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UNIMI's Action Plan for CoARA Progress Report – 2026

CoARA
Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

Action Plan 2022-2027: Monitoring of Activities 2025

This document provides an initial systematic monitoring of the actions set out in the Action Plan for the implementation of CoARA commitments, as defined within the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

The Action Plan of the University of Milan, published in June 2024, is available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12582372>. The objective of this report is to assess the state of progress of the actions and the results achieved, highlighting any critical issues where relevant.

For each action, the monitoring is structured in tables including:

- the relevant CoARA core and supporting commitments;
- a description of the action;
- the implementation timeline, referring to the Agreement timeframe (2022–2027) or to periodic milestones;
- the responsible actors and involved structures;
- the link to the University's Strategic Plan objectives and to the Action Plan intervention areas;
- a summary of the state of progress 18 months after publication.

This structure aims to ensure the traceability of actions, support continuous monitoring of progress, and foster the integration of the CoARA Action Plan into the University's planning, programming, and evaluation processes..

This document has been prepared by the Performance, Quality Assurance, Assessment, and Open Science Policy Division, based on a model developed by the Polytechnic University of Turin. <https://zenodo.org/records/19609871>

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Commitment 1: Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.

Action	Introduction of a Third Mission and an OS dimension in the salary increment procedures (e.g. it is asked to include relevant achievements, including not only publications, but also datasets, software, services, and so on).
Timeline	From 2025
Indicators	
Responsibility	Vice Rector for research, Delegate for Third Mission
Structures Involved	HR,
Strategic Plan	
State of the art	Realized
Outcome of the Action	Greater attention to third mission activities and their reporting

Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

Action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ad hoc courses will be provided for early career researchers to raise awareness toward fair and equitable (open) peer review. 2) Publication of a regulation on the acceptable use of AI in research activities. 3) The university is also committed, as it has been in the past, to organizing events on qualitative assessment and its implementation in different disciplinary areas.
Timeline	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 2024 a pilot training; from 2025 a regular training. 2) 2025. 3) Starting from 2024.
Indicators	
Responsibility	Vice Rector for Digital Transformation and Artificial Intelligence. AI WG
Structures Involved	ICT, DPO support office, Open science Division
Strategic Plan	System-level objectives
State of the art	Realized
Outcome of the Action	Training modules on AI for administrative and research staff. Training modules on research evaluation for researchers and PHD students. Training modules on open peer review for researchers and PHD students.

Commitment 3: Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.

Action	Guidelines for the internal commissions (respectful of the ministerial rules) will be issued and their implementation will be monitored
Timeline	From 2025
Indicators	
Responsibilities	Vice Rector for research/Governing bodies
Structures Involved	HR, Open science Division, Research Division
Strategic Plan	✓
State of the art	Ongoing
Outcome of the Action	Guidelines for commissions which help them to evaluate researchers in a fair way

Commitment 4: Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.

Action	Progressive and further reduction in participation in rankings, along with better and more complete communication of what the university does and its strengths.
Timeline	From 2025.
Indicators	
Responsibility	Vice Rector for research
Structures Involved	Communication and institutional events division
Strategic Plan	
State of the art	Some rankings are monitored, but they are not used to evaluate departments or disciplinary areas, nor to inform strategic planning
Outcome of the Action	A better understanding of the limited value of rankings

Commitment 5: Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.

Action	Among the first signatories of the Barcelona declaration, the university is engaged and will engage in the implementation of multidimensional public dashboards. The first one will describe the university's collaborations and their intensity. Collaboration with the Computer science department and other universities will be crucial.
Timeline	Ongoing.
Indicators	
Responsibility	Vice Rector for research
Structures Involved	Open science division
Strategic Plan	
State of the art	No proprietary data used for monitoring activities; development of indicators with OpenAIRE (MoU) and other Italian institution
Outcome of the Action	Reports and dashboards that use only not-proprietary data

Commitment 6: Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes – 6.1 (Criteria for units and institutions): with the direct involvement of research organisations and researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria for assessing research units and research performing organisations, while promoting interoperability.

Action	Initiating advocacy efforts toward the region and ministries (Health and Research Ministries) together with other COARA signatories.
Timeline	Starting from 2025
Indicators	
Responsibility	Coordinators of the National Chapter
Structures Involved	Open science division, Research Division, HR
Strategic Plan	
State of the art	ongoing
Outcome of the Action	

Commitment 6: Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes – 6.2. (criteria for projects and researchers): with the direct involvement of researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria, tools and processes for the assessment of research projects, research teams and researchers that are adapted to their context of application.

Action	Analysis and review of indicators used for different processes, starting with internal ones: distribution of university funds, salary increases.
Timeline	From 2025
Indicators	
Responsibility	Vice Rector for Research
Structures Involved	HR, Open science Division, Research Division
Strategic Plan	✓
State of the art	Ongoing
Outcome of the Action	Inclusion of new dimensions in the evaluation processes (open access, open science, public engagement)

Commitment 7: Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.

Action	The University already offers courses on evaluation, the distorting effects of entirely quantitative evaluation with a warning, however, also to so-called predatory peer review practices and review mills. The university plans to increase training on evaluation criteria particularly the pros and cons of quantitative and qualitative systems.
Timeline	From 2024
Indicators	
Responsibility	Vice Rector for Research
Structures Involved	Open science Division
Strategic Plan	✓
State of the art	Courses are offered on a regularly basis
Outcome of the Action	

Commitment 8: Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.

Action	Continue with the exchange of experience and information with members of the national chapter and in the different working groups.
Timeline	Ongoing
Indicators	
Responsibility	Vice Rector for research/WG of the national chapter
Structures Involved	Open science division
Strategic Plan	✓
State of the art	ongoing
Outcome of the Action	Mutual learning of best practices

Commitment 9: Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.

Action	Publishing our CoARA roadmap on public platforms once finalized and monitoring its implementation.
Timeline	From 2024
Indicators	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12582372
Responsibility	Vice Rector for Research
Structures Involved	Open science division
Strategic Plan	
State of the art	Realized
Outcome of the Action	

Commitment 10: Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

Azione	Monitoring of the different dimension of open science, publication of reports on the different aspects (also critical) of open science.
Timeline	Ongoing
Indicators	
Responsability	Vice rector for Research
Structures involved	Open science Division/Research Division
Strategic Plan	✓
State of the art	Ongoing
Outcome of the action	Using evidence to shape research policy